

ON THE EFFECTS OF THERMAL EXPANSION IN METAL-MATRIX-COMPOSITES

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Abstract

Based on a qualitative argument, it is shown that the detrimental effect due to differential thermal expansion existing between fiber and metal-matrix in MMC (metal-matrix composite) is minimized for shorter fibers. The "ideal" aspect ratio for fibers found experimental in MMC is also justifiable within the same argument.

In meeting the ever-increasing demand for materials with superior mechanical properties, the MMC (metal-matrix composite) has played an important role. In general, the fiber materials used in forming MMCs are nonmetals, e.g., boron, SiC, TiC, glass graphite. Therefore, MMCs have an inherent (physical, chemical, and/or metallurgical) incompatibility problem between the nonmetal fiber on one hand and the metal-matrix on the other. One of the most serious physical incompatibilities between fiber and metal-matrix lies in their differential thermal expansion. Within the temperature range, 0° - 1200°C, in which MMCs are expected to perform, the linear thermal expansion coefficients for metals and nonmetals are in the neighborhood of $10-30 \times 10^{-6}$ and $3-10 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ respectively(1). This represents three to five times greater thermal expansion in the metal-matrix than in fibers. This physical incompatibility is one of the major causes for the fast thermal degradation of mechanical properties in composites (2,3).

The purpose of this note is to show in a qualitative manner:

- (a) Why the detrimental effect of this physical incompatibility (Differential thermal expansion) on MMC is less where discontinuous short fibers are used.
- (b) How the well-known ideal fiber aspect ratio in MMC(4,5,6) can be understood from the same line of reasoning used in (a).

Let us assume equal volumes (V_0) of fiber and of metal-matrix at 0°C. In order to simulate the fiber shape, we shall write the volume of the fiber as,

$$V_0 = N \cdot L \cdot A \quad \text{where } A - \text{finite constant fiber cross section.}$$

$$L - \text{fiber length.}$$

$$N - \text{number of fibers (with } A \text{ and } L).$$

If the two materials are in their "free" (unbonded) states, and the temperature is raised from 0°C to a certain high temperature, T, the final volumes for the two materials will be:

$$V_m = V_0 + V_0 \int_0^T K_m dT \quad (1)$$

$$V_f = V_0 + V_0 \int_0^T K_f dT \quad (2)$$

where K_m and K_f are the respective volume thermal expansion coefficients of the metal-matrix and the fiber.

We now consider the case where fibers are dispersed uniformly throughout the matrix and are metallurgically bonded (without chemical interaction at the interface) throughout the temperature range considered. Again, the temperature is raised from 0°C to T°C. Forming a MMC at 0°C and raising the temperature to a certain high temperature T°C is completely equivalent (in terms of the arguments presented here) to forming a MMC at T°C and lowering the temperature to 0°C, which is the way MMCs are usually prepared. If the fiber strength and modulus are much higher than that of the metal-matrix (this, invariably is the case experimentally), then the thermal expansion of the metal-matrix will be constrained (limited) roughly to the extent of the fiber expansion. The volume strain created in the metal-matrix due to such constraint is:

$$V_m - V_f = \Delta V = V_o \int_0^T (K_m - K_f) dT = V_o \int_0^T \Delta K dT \quad \text{or}$$

$$\Delta V/V_o = \int_0^T \Delta K dT \quad (3)$$

It is clear that the volume strain created in the metal-matrix is a function of temperature, T , and ΔK , the thermal expansion difference between the two materials. Thus, a given T and ΔK will yield a given volume strain, $\Delta V/V_o$. Corresponding to this volume strain there will exist a volume stress, σ_m , which can be determined if the stress-strain curve for the metal-matrix at temperature, T , (as depicted in Figure 1)

1. Stress-strain curve of metal-matrix at temperature, T .

is known. By definition, $\sigma_m = P_m / (\Delta V/V_o)$, where P_m is the total residual pressure. Since the thermal expansion mismatch exists principally at the interface between fiber and metal-matrix, P_m , is expected to be concentrated at the interface. Thus, our interest is in finding σ_s , the residual stress at the interface. Following the stress-strain relationship σ_s can be estimated as, $\sigma_s = P_m/S$ (where S is the total area of interface between fiber and matrix).

Inasmuch as the total area of interface is directly proportional to N , and inversely proportional to L (for a given fixed fiber volume fraction), it follows that:

$$P_m \propto \sigma_s \cdot N \quad \text{or} \quad \propto \sigma_s \cdot (1/L) \quad (4)$$

For a given P_m , the σ_s as a function of N (or $1/L$) is shown in Figure 2. It is clear the shorter L (or greater the number N) yields

2. Plot of σ_s as a function of $N(1/L)$.

smaller σ_s and the more stable is the MMC. This, therefore, demonstrates qualitatively the advantage of short fibers in a MMC under thermal fluctuation, i.e., for a constant volume percent of fiber in a MMC, the σ_s generated by the differential thermal expansion between fiber and metal-matrix will be smaller for shorter fibers.

If the fiber has a proportional (critical) limit, σ_p , at temperature, T , the following conditions with regard to the mechanical behavior of the fiber at temperature T can be stated. For $\sigma_s > \sigma_p$ ($\sigma_s < \sigma_p$) fibers in MMC will (will not) fracture. Simultaneously, the σ_p will also set the critical length, L_c , for fibers in a given MMC. Fibers with lengths longer than the length, L_c , in the MMC at temperature T , will fracture, fibers with length shorter than L_c will not. Since different temperature limits will yield different values of $\Delta V/V_0$ (and subsequently different values of σ_m , and P_m), different σ_s vs. $1/L$ curves will result. For a given σ_p associated with the fiber, this means different L_c 's as illustrated in Figure 2.

It is a known fact that a fiber (or filament) in a metal-matrix will create a stress, σ , concentrated at the fiber tip (7,8). The total tip-stress, σ_t , will therefore be directly proportional to the number of tips, or the number of fibers, i.e., $\sigma_t = 2N\sigma$. If the number N is large and if the fibers are randomly distributed equally in all directions, the total residual stress, σ_T , can be equated to a simple algebraic sum of the two residual stresses, σ_s and σ_t . This relationship is graphically shown in Figure 3. The σ_T thus obtained shows a minimum corresponding to N_m or $1/L_m$. For fibers with a finite cross section, A (therefore a constant diameter), the L_m can be utilized to obtain the "ideal" aspect ratio for

3. Plot of σ_T , the total residual stress (the sum of σ_s -interface stress and σ_t -tip stress) as a function $N(1/L)$, indicating a minimum corresponding to L_m .

the fiber. That is at this length, L_m (and diameter) the residual stress, σ_T is at its minimum and thus the MMC is expected to yield the largest MSF (matrix-strengthening-factor) as observed experimentally in MMC(9,10,11).

It is of interest to extend the analysis described herein to the particle-dispersed MMC systems. Since in these systems the particles are roughly spherical, no tip stresses are expected and the total stress, σ_T , is therefore dependent only on σ_s . It can be seen from Figure 2 that in this case the σ_s is lower for smaller L (or smaller particle diameter). Therefore, the MSF will be larger for smaller diameter particles as observed experimentally(12,13,14). In this manner, the noted difference(15) between particle dispersed and fiber-dispersed systems as a function of particle size and/or fiber aspect ratio can all be reconciled.

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